

MS14

Dataset of the results of the large-scale choice and the behavioural economic experiment

Lead Beneficiary: 12 - James Hutton Institute
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Milestone Description & Contributors

- **Due date:** February 28th, 2025
- **Actual submission date:** February 28th, 2025
- **Project start date:** September 1st, 2021
- **Duration:** 48 months
- **Work package:** WP5
- **Work package leader:** Bálint Bálazs
- **Milestone Title:** "Dataset of the results of the large-scale choice and the behavioural economic experiments"

- **Mean of Verification**

Results collection of the WP5 associated experiments will be completed.

1. Milestone description

Milestone 14 is based on the activities undertaken within **Task 5.3** “Farmers’ and consumers’ expectations and preferences for UCs”, under the leadership of The James Hutton Institute and with the support of local partners. T5.3 aimed to assess **consumers’ preferences** with respect to five underutilised crops (UCs) from different pedoclimatic zones by conducting large-scale online choice experiments focused on food products derived from those same crops. It also aimed to assess **farmers’ preferences** for the attributes of a single, best-fit-for-purpose UC and their decision-making and preferences for the public goods (including non-monetary goods) delivered by UCs, respectively through a large-scale online choice experiment and a behavioural experiments (public good game) also conducted online.

The consumers’ samples were **stratified** based on age (<35, 35-65, and >65) and gender (male or female), cross-tabulated to obtain six strata whose sizes were set in line with the national population. The responses were further filtered based on **quality criteria**, namely: at least 2.5 seconds spent on each choice card, median time spent on the cards of at least 5 seconds, total survey duration over 7 minutes, failure of at most one attention check out of two present in the questionnaire, no “straightlining” in the Likert scales (visually assessed). The farmers’ sample was not stratified, but we included an initial filtering question about the job of the respondent. Additionally, we registered five **quality indicators**, namely: at least 2.5 seconds spent on each choice card, median time spent on the cards of at least 5 seconds, total survey duration above 1/3 of the median survey duration, time spent on the instructions of the public good game over 1/3 of the median time, and no “straightlining” in the Likert scales (assessed via standard deviations). The respondents that do not meet one or more of these quality indicators can be excluded from the final sample as a robustness check, if required.

Below, we list the UCs selected for the consumers’ surveys, the derived food product, the country, the date of implementation of the survey, and the sample sizes achieved.

- 1) **Bere barley (shortbread biscuits)** produced with its flour). In the workshop, the focus was on **Bere flour**, but the research team decided to switch to a specific bakery product following recommendations by the consumers. The survey was conducted among **consumers** in **Scotland** relying on the market research company Prolific between February 23 and March 27, 2024. The sample size is 301 (1,790 choices).¹
- 2) **Hanging tomatoes** (to be consumed raw). The workshop focused on **Tomaca de Penjar de Benlloc**, but the research team decided to extend to hanging tomatoes in general, given the very specific and localised nature of that variety. The survey was conducted among **consumers** in **Spain** relying on the market research company TGM Research between January 16-22, 2025. The sample size is 345 (2,070 choices).
- 3) **IDEAL tomato** (to be consumed raw). The survey was conducted among **consumers** in **Bulgaria** relying on the market research company TGM Research between November 7-30, 2024. The sample size is 336 (2,016 choices).
- 4) **Yellow pea and einkorn wheat (pasta)** made with yellow pea protein and einkorn wheat flour). In the workshop, the focus was exclusively on yellow pea, although einkorn flour was one of the attributes, but the research team decided to refer more explicitly to einkorn as an UC (ancient cereal). The survey was conducted among **consumers** in **Italy** relying on the market research company TGM Research between January 30 and February 7, 2025. The sample size is 347 (2,082 choices).
- 5) **Mixtures of underutilised gramineous and leguminous fodder crops (Parmigiano Reggiano)** cheese produced with the milk of cows fed with those crops). The survey was conducted among **consumers** in **Italy** relying on the market research company TGM Research between February 20-25, 2025. The sample size is 280 (1,680 choices).²

¹ Some consumers did not complete all the choices, but we decided to retain them all the same due to the more limited availability of respondents in Scotland; in other surveys, the consumers or farmers had to complete the survey in full in order to be retained.

² Although the sample size is already sufficient for the analysis and larger than planned, the survey will be kept open for some more days until March 2025 to increase the numbers.

The farmers' survey was conducted among **Italian crop farmers** with the support of IPSOS Europe, between November 18-25, 2024. The survey included a two-round **public goods game** with four theoretical scenarios in the second round that focused on a non-specified underutilised variety of a standard crop grown by the respondents, and a **choice experiment** focused on **yellow pea**, similar to those tested in the Melfi (Italy) workshop in May 2024, but with more alternative legumes to cover farmers from all the pedoclimatic zones of Italy. The version including the public good game was assigned to 50% of the respondents, randomly selected. The final **sample size** is **331 farmers** (1,986 choices), of which **186** took part in the public good game (744 scenario responses), and the rest responded to the choice experiment only. If the responses are filtered based on all the quality criteria listed above, the sample size becomes **220** (1,296 choices), of which **108** participants in the public good game. Indeed, the specificity of the sample and the complexity of the survey (which was kept as such on purpose, in line with the complexity of the incentives foreseen by the Common Agricultural Policy, highlighted during the CREATOR workshop) resulted in a large number of non-compliances.

The consumers and farmers' survey experiments were **pre-registered** to ensure rigorousness, and the preregistrations can be accessed at the following links:

- a. **Consumers:** <https://aspredicted.org/9ths-w8bk.pdf>;
- b. **Farmers:** <https://aspredicted.org/85cj-m4ry.pdf>.

2. Mean of Verification

Have you provided the Mean of Verification described in the GA? Yes

The datasets are securely stored in the drives of The James Hutton Institute as well as in the Basecamp repository at <https://public.3.basecamp.com/p/BoS6axXoknuPtgMZiNZCwGix/vault>.

They will be prepared for open access publication (with embargo) in an online repository, e.g. Zenodo, before the end of the RADIANT project. The analysis of the choice data, behavioural experimental data, and stated preferences will be conducted within M43 and M46 of the RADIANT project, and presented within Deliverable D5.3 "Farmers' and consumers' preferences and behavioural economics underpinning UC choice."